

production and economic return, appropriate rice and wheat varieties must be selected.

Six rice - wheat cropping patterns were tested at three sites of the North Bangladesh Tubewell Project, Thakurgaon, during 1981-82 and agro-economic analysis was used to determine the most productive, profitable rice - wheat combinations.

BR4, BR10, and Pajam rices yielded more than BR11, Kalam, and Malshara. Pavon wheat yielded more than Balaka, Jupateca, and Sonalika (see table). BR4 - Pavon and Pajam - Pavon rice - wheat combinations yielded more and had higher net return and benefit-cost ratios than BR10 with Balaka and two local

Agroeconomic performance of six rice - wheat cropping patterns. Thakurgaon, Bangladesh, 1981-82.

Cropping pattern			Mean yield (t/ha)		Gross return ^c /pattern (\$/ha)	Net return /pattern (\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
Rice		Wheat	Rice	Wheat			
BR4 ^a	-	Pavon	4.4	2.9	1312	792	2.5
BR10 ^a	-	Balaka	3.4	2.3	1027	566	2.2
BR11 ^a	-	Jupateca	3.0	1.6	822	384	1.9
Pajam	-	Pavon	3.8	2.7	1179	666	2.3
Kalam ^b	-	Sonalika	2.3	1.6	708	244	1.5
Malshara ^b	-	Sonalika	1.7	1.4	562	147	1.3

^aHigh-yielding variety. ^bLocal variety. ^cRice price = \$160.74/ton; wheat price = \$207.62/ton.

varieties with Sonalika. Cost of growing local rice varieties generally was low, but low yield potential reduced profits. Local photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties also are harvested late, and delayed planting

of Sonalika wheat, which reduced its yield. With an assured water supply, BR4 - Pavon and Pajam - Pavon can be grown successfully in the Thakurgaon tubewell project. □

Performance of rice-based cropping patterns in the irrigated uplands of Orissa

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Rice, planted on more than 4 million ha, is the major crop in Orissa. We studied the following rice-based cropping at the Bhubaneswar Research Farm in 1981-82:

1. rice (Annapurna) — rice (Jagannath) — rice (Jaya),
2. rice (Annapurna) — groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*, variety AK12-24) — ragi (*Eleusine coracana*, variety Dibyasingh),
3. rice (Jaya) — potato (*Solanum tuberosum*, variety Kufri Sinduri) — sesamum (*Sesamum indicum*, variety B67),
4. rice (Annapurna) — maize (*Zea mays*, variety Jawahar composite) — cowpea (*Vigna sinensis*, variety SEB2),
5. jute (*Corchorus* sp., variety JRC212) — rice (Jagannath) — groundnut (AK12-24), and
6. rice (Jaya) — knolkhol (*Brassica oleracea*, variety Caulorapa) — lady's finger (*Abelmoschus esculantus*, variety Pusa Sawani).

Annapurna was drilled and Jaya was transplanted. There are three crop seasons: kharif (Jul-Oct), rabi (Nov-Feb), and summer (Mar-Jun). In 1981-82 rain-fall was 1,120 mm in kharif, 51 mm in

Duration, grain yield, and total dry matter production of crop patterns in Orissa, India.

Cropping pattern no.	Crop	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)						Total dry wt (t/ha)
			Grain	Straw	Others ^a				
					Edible		Nonedible		
					F	D	F	D	
1	Rice	70	2.9	4.5	-	-	-	-	7.4
	Rice	98	3.9	5.0	-	-	-	-	8.9
	Rice	115	4.6	6.9	-	-	-	-	11.5
	Total	283	11.4	16.4	-	-	-	-	27.8
2	Rice	110	4.3	6.1	-	-	-	-	10.4
	Groundnut	120	-	-	-	2.6	8.2	2.3	4.9
	Ragi	85	2.4	3.5	-	-	-	-	5.9
Total	315	6.7	9.6	-	2.6	8.2	2.3	21.2	
3	Rice	110	4.6	6.8	-	-	-	-	11.4
	Potato	110	-	-	16.8	3.1	15.1	2.5	5.6
	Sesamum	95	0.8	1.6	-	-	4.5	2.1	4.5
Total	315	5.4	8.4	16.8	3.1	19.6	4.6	21.5	
4	Rice	110	4.5	6.7	-	-	-	-	11.2
	Maize	95	3.8	-	-	-	-	5.0	8.8
	Cowpea	80	-	-	3.6	0.5	4.4	0.8	1.3
	Total	285	8.3	6.7	3.6	0.5	4.4	5.8	21.3
5	Jute	132	-	-	-	-	-	3.0 F ^a 4.5 S ^b	7.5
	Rice	100	3.7	5.5	-	-	-	-	9.2
Groundnut	120	-	-	-	-	2.5	-	3.1	5.6
	Total	352	3.1	5.5	-	2.5	-	10.6	22.3
6	Rice	110	4.5	6.6	-	-	-	-	11.1
	Knolkhol	60	-	-	8.3	1.1	5.0	0.8	1.9
	Lady's finger	70	-	-	4.1	0.6	6.7	2.0	2.6
	Total	240	4.5	6.6	13.0	1.7	11.7	2.8	15.6
CD (0.05)									0.68

^aF = fiber, D = dry matter. ^bS = sticks.

rabi, and 306 mm in summer. Kharif rice and jute were rainfed and the rabi and summer crops received irrigation when

necessary.

Of the cropping patterns evaluated, jute - rice - groundnut used the max-

imum (352) cropped days/year (see table). Rice – rice – rice used 283 days, and rice plus 2 vegetable crops (rice – knolkhol – lady’s finger) used 240 days.

Three rice crops produced maximum grain yield (11 t/ha) followed by rice –

maize – cowpea, with 8.3 t grain/ha. Rice – rice – rice yielded significantly more dry matter, followed by jute – rice – groundnut. Rice – knolkhol – lady’s finger yielded the least dry matter.

Results indicate that three sequential

rice crops give highest grain yield, and that rice – maize – cowpea can be grown to obtain reasonable grain yields with more efficient soil and water management. □

Water table depths and dynamics aid interpretation of drought-prone rainfed lowland rice variety trials

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During the 1980 to 1982 wet seasons, we assessed the effects of water table depth in 11 environments in the Philippines on grain yield of elite and advanced breeding materials of the Rainfed Lowland Yield Trial for Drought-Prone Areas.

Polyvinylchloride tubes placed in the field to a depth of 20 cm and 60 or 100 cm were observation wells for measuring the water table depth. Average water table depth (AWD) during the yield-determining reproductive and grain-filling stages was calculated by summing the daily values from panicle initiation to 10 d before harvest. Plants are most sensitive to water stress at these stages. Water table depth was summed individually for each maturity class: very early (<105 d), early (105-115 d), medium (115-130 d), and late (>130 d).

Figure 1 shows the relationship of average water table depth and grain yield for each maturity group. Each point is an average of the two highest yielding varieties or lines for each location. By using the highest yielding entries we hoped to negate the effects of other biological and physical-chemical factors that determine growth and yield, and thus focus on the role of subsurface water in rainfed wet-land culture.

There was a significant correlation for all but the medium-maturity entries in the shallow water table.

In the deeper water table, correlation was significant for all but the early maturing group. Grain yield generally decreased as water table depth decreased regardless of maturity group.

At some sites where water table depth during the crop season was very low, we obtained high grain yield. This might have

1. Relationship between grain yield of the 2 highest yielding entries at each location and average water table depth in the root zone above the hardpan (0 to 20 cm) and below the paddy (0 to 60 or 100 cm) soil surface. The average water table depths were summed from 30 d before flowering to 20 days after flowering based on mean flowering date of each maturity group.

2. Water level in paddy (piezometer at 20 cm) and below the paddy (piezometer at 60 cm), and rainfall at Oton, Iloilo, Philippines, 1981 wet season.

been caused by adequate amount and distribution of rainfall, and not total rainfall. For example, at Iloilo in 1981 wet season (Fig. 2), rainfall was well distributed from 10 d before flowering to 20 d after flowering, with a total rainfall of

154 mm for the early-maturing group and a mean grain yield of 3.9 t/ha.

At Guimba in 1980 wet season, rainfall was high (347 mm) during the same growth stages but mean grain yield was low, 2.1 t/ha, because of a short-term